

Human health in the global plastics treaty: Summary ahead of INC 5.2

Why is human health important in the Global Plastics Treaty?

- The right to enjoy the highest attainable standard of health,¹ and to a safe, clean, healthy, and sustainable environment² are fundamental human rights.
- Human health is a critical consideration for guiding the identification and evaluation of responses to plastic pollution.
- Human disease and premature mortality associated with plastics presents a substantial cost to society, including through burdens on healthcare systems and lost productivity.³ A successful treaty will mitigate these public health costs.
- Exposure to plastics begins in the womb⁴ and continues throughout the entire human lifespan.⁵
- Scientific evidence highlights health concerns that must be explicitly addressed in the treaty to mitigate harms caused by plastics, for example chemicals contained in plastics that migrate during normal use⁵⁻⁷ and throughout plastics life cycles.⁵
- Alternatives and substitutes to plastics may also have harmful impacts on human health.^{8, 9} Measures in the treaty should ensure the safety and sustainability of these alternatives: in particular, by establishing health-centred criteria for reducing and replacing plastics, which can help to avoid regrettable substitutions.¹⁰

How can the Global Plastics Treaty protect human health?

There is consensus amongst global health experts, including the World Health Organization, that protecting human health is a priority in the treaty.¹¹⁻¹³ This can be achieved by combining a stand alone article (Art. 19) on health with comprehensive integration of health throughout relevant provisions, including inter alia the following:

- **Ensuring a clear objective to protect human health across all stages of the plastics lifecycle** (Preamble, Article 1).
- **Adopting legally binding global targets to reduce plastics production** (Articles 3 and 6).
- **Reducing the overall number of chemicals**

used to make plastics¹⁴ and eliminating hazardous substances, for example by restricting entire groups of concern (Articles 3 and 5).

- **Establishing safety criteria for plastics and their alternatives across all lifecycle stages, including safe product design** (Article 5).
- **Promoting mandatory transparency and traceability throughout all stages of the plastics lifecycle** (Articles 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 17, 18).
- **Preventing blanket sectoral exemptions, including for the health sector** (there are no provisions in current Chair's text, formerly under Article 1bis: Scope).
- **Providing mechanisms to support and integrate emerging science following the adoption of the treaty** (Articles 3 + Annex, 5, 6, 19, 20 and 24).
- **Including health considerations to guide financing criteria** (Article 11).

What are key relevant scientific considerations on plastics and health?

- **Plastic chemicals and micro- and nanoplastics (MNPs) are released throughout all plastics life stages.**⁵ This begins from plastics production and transportation, including spills of plastic pellets¹⁵, during the use phase (from tyres, textiles, food packaging), from plastic waste management¹⁶ (landfill, incineration, recycling) and mismanagement (open burning, dumpsites)¹⁷ and the weathering of plastics in the environment.⁴
- Plastic products and microplastics also **leach hazardous chemicals and chemicals that have not been tested for safety** into food⁶ and the environment.⁴ These chemicals enter human bodies through ingestion, inhalation and dermal absorption.¹⁸ The chemical composition of plastics lacks transparency.¹⁹
- At least **1481 plastic chemicals have been found to migrate from food contact materials** into foods, making human exposure very likely.⁶ At least **1396 plastic chemicals are present in human bodies**, including several with reliable causal links to health impacts.⁸

- Plastic products are a **source of MNPs**, including from their normal and intended use, for example, as food contact materials.²¹
- Emerging studies show that **MNPs have been detected in several organs of the human body (including human blood, placenta, liver, and kidney)**, and may be associated with adverse health outcomes.⁴ More research is needed to understand MNPs in the human body and how they impact health.⁴
- **Reusing and recycling plastics leads to MNP generation and the release of plastic chemicals**, human exposure and environmental emissions.^{16, 22} The contamination with, and accumulation of, **hazardous chemicals in recycled and reused plastic products** has been demonstrated.^{16, 23}
- **Greenhouse gases are emitted across the plastics lifecycle, particularly during extraction, production and open burning.**⁵ This results in direct and indirect human health impacts from rising temperatures, extreme weather events, infectious diseases and disrupted food systems.²⁴
- **Exposure to toxic substances from plastics production to poorly regulated and unsafe recycling and recovery practices** poses serious occupational and public health risks to workers and fenceline communities, especially in informal and low-resource settings,^{5, 22} raising urgent concerns for environmental justice and health equity.¹⁶
- **Air pollution is a leading cause of global human disease and mortality.**²⁵ Plastics are predominantly produced from petrochemicals. High levels of air pollution are found near petrochemical production and processing facilities, which can exceed safe levels.²⁶ Open burning of plastics and urban fires also release chemicals and black carbon to the air, elevating risks of respiratory diseases.^{27, 28}
- **Macroplastic waste can compromise sanitation and energy systems**, exacerbate flooding,²⁹ spread invasive species harmful to local biodiversity,³⁰ transmit pathogens,³¹ and act as breeding grounds for disease vectors.³²
- **Plastics, plastic chemicals and MNPs have significant effects on wildlife and ecosystems** which directly and indirectly impair human health, as considered under the One Health approach.³³

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